

Knowledge and Attitude of Babcock University Undergraduate Students Towards Sickle Cell Anaemia

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Abstract

Sickle cell anaemia is a major public health problem accounting for more than 300,000 babies born each year with the disease. Its highest burden is found in Nigeria with about 20-30 per 1000 births. The study examined knowledge and attitude of undergraduate students in Babcock University towards sickle cell anaemia. The purpose of the study was to assess the level of knowledge of undergraduate students in Babcock University about sickle cell anaemia and to assess their attitude towards sickle cell anaemia. A descriptive cross-sectional study design was adopted. Multi-stage sampling procedure was employed to select a sample size of 360. A validated questionnaire was administered to the respondents and data collected were subjected to descriptive and inferential statistics. Results showed a moderate level of knowledge 290(80.6%) and majority 267(74.2%) had a negative attitude towards sickle cell anaemia. Also a positive relationship between the level of knowledge and attitude towards the disease was observed. In conclusion, information dissemination about the disease should be intensified both by the government and private sectors as well as religious bodies and schools. In this way, intending couples will be encouraged to go for premarital genetic testing, newborn screenings and counselling and thus make better-informed decisions based on test results and promote the prevention of the disease.

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Introduction

Sickle cell anaemia is accepted as a global health issue as it has been reported to be the most prevalent monogenic disease in the world today. (Pule, et al, 2017). Its burden is on the increase with about 300,000 babies being born with severe forms of haemoglobinopathies on a yearly basis (Centre for Disease Control and prevention, 2015). In the United States alone, it was estimated that about 100,000 Americans are affected by sickle cell anaemia (CDC, 2019) while in Europe, a prevalence rate of 43.12 per 100,000 was reported (Wastnedge, et al, 2018). It predominates in sub-Saharan Africa, East Mediterranean areas, Middle-East, India and Nigeria being the most populous black nation in the world, bears its greatest burden (Ademola, 2015). About 24% of the Nigerian population are carriers of the mutant gene and a prevalence of about 20-30 per 1000 births is seen (Adegoke, Adekile & Adeodu, 2015).

In sickle cell disease, the normal round shape of red blood cells become like crescent moons, they interconnect and can result in blood clots which cause extreme pain in the back, chest, hands and feet. The majority of children with the most severe form of the disease die before the age of 5, usually from an infection or severe blood loss (World Health Organisation, 2017). The cause of the disease is mainly genetic where in a person receives one defective gene from both parents to develop the disease while a person that receives one defective and one healthy gene remains healthy even though he/she has the sickle cell trait (Ameen, et al, 2016). Its management and treatment modalities have greatly improved with increasing research over the past 10 years aimed at decreasing painful crises and improving the quality of life of patients with the disease and they include long-term treatment with hydroxyurea, imaging studies, bone marrow transplants, blood transfusion programmes as well as gene therapy which is still under study (WHO, 2017).

Ugwu (2016) further buttressed that knowledge about sickle cell anaemia is a way of controlling its scourge and stands as a method of preventing the condition but despite the large number of people affected by the sickle cell anaemia there still exists gaps in knowledge about the disease. In Babcock university, positive attitude towards sickle cell anaemia has been noticed based on several interactions held by the researcher with students but a good number of the undergraduate students still lacked knowledge about the disease even among those studying health related courses and the few who have negative attitudes, do not have good knowledge of the disease. This brought about the need for a study to assess the knowledge and attitude of Babcock university undergraduate students towards sickle cell anaemia.

An intervention study aimed at providing knowledge about sickle cell anaemia via health education, its effect on the knowledge and attitude of respondents towards the disease and its prevention was conducted by Olatona, et al. (2012), only 25.3% of respondents had good knowledge about sickle cell disease and screening pre-intervention but after the intervention, knowledge of the disease and screening increased by 64.1% significantly and a good number of respondents demonstrated better attitude towards the condition. It was shown in the above study that a lack of knowledge hereby could pose a threat to effectively curbing and reducing the prevalence of the disease. Several studies that assessed the knowledge of sickle cell anaemia have noted the presence of a low or high level of knowledge among respondents. Those who had good knowledge were seen to either have relatives or friends who had the disease or had a higher level of education (Boadu, 2018). Orish, et al (2014) found relatively high level of knowledge about sickle cell disease of about 93.4% while about 6.6% had no knowledge at all in a study conducted in Ghana. It is against this

background that the researcher examines the knowledge and attitude towards sickle cell anaemia among undergraduate students in Babcock University. This study specifically:

1. determined the level of knowledge of undergraduate students in Babcock University about sickle cell anaemia;
2. assessed the attitudes of undergraduate students in Babcock University towards sickle cell anaemia; and
3. examined the relationship between the level of knowledge of sickle cell anaemia and attitude towards sickle cell anaemia.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study:

1. What is the level of knowledge of undergraduate students in Babcock University about sickle cell anaemia?
2. What are the attitudes of undergraduate students in Babcock University towards sickle cell anaemia?

Research Hypothesis

This hypothesis was postulated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between the level of knowledge of sickle cell anaemia and attitude towards sickle cell anaemia.

Methodology

The study utilised a descriptive cross-sectional study design to assess the knowledge and practices towards sickle cell anaemia among undergraduate students in Babcock University, Ilishan-remo, Ogun state. The population of interest included undergraduate students currently running a bachelor degree program. A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed in this study to select sample size of 360. In the first stage of sampling, the researcher used simple balloting to select four (4) schools out of eight (8). In the second stage, proportionate sampling was utilized in determining the number of students per school. Convenience sampling was used in the final stage to get to each participant based on those who were present during the data collection process.

Data collection was done using a self-structured questionnaire derived from literature review. The questionnaire was organized in accordance with the research objectives and hypotheses. It had 3 sections namely section A, B and C. To ensure validity, the instrument was validated by experts of Tests and Measurement and Nursing. Reviews and corrections were adequately carried out in restructuring the instrument before usage. The internal consistency method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. The instrument was administered on 10% of the sample size in order to test the reliability of the instrument. Cronbach's Alpha statistics was used to analysed the collected data which yielded coefficient value of 0.811 for the reliability.

Data were collected with the aid of the questionnaire. The researcher ensured that the respondents were adequately informed about the purpose of the study and assured them of their confidentiality and anonymity. This was explained before the questionnaires were distributed and the period of data collection was estimated to be 5 days. The researcher collected data with the aid of research assistants who were trained on the method of data collection and the distribution took place in classrooms and halls of residence. Statistical analysis was done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0 software.

The data collected were subjected to descriptive and inferential statistics. Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of knowledge of undergraduate students in Babcock University about sickle cell anaemia?

Table 1: Respondents' Knowledge of Sickle cell anaemia **n = 360**

Variables	Yes	No
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
A genetic disorder inherited from only a single parent	96(26.7)	261(72.5)
A genetic disorder inherited from both parents	334(92.8)	26(7.2)
Results from deficiency of red blood cells	298(82.8)	62(17.2)
The red blood cells in sickle cell anaemia are shaped like a sickle	310(86.1)	50(13.9)
A person who has sickle cell anaemia has the SS genotype	333(92.5)	27(7.5)
Can be contracted from someone who has the disease	86(23.9)	274(76.1)
Is gotten from bad food	23(6.4)	337(93.6)
Is caused by infection from microorganism	66(18.3)	294(81.7)
Is associated with frequent pain episodes	299(83.1)	61(16.9)
Can cause partial or complete blindness	105(29.2)	255(70.8)
A sickle cell carrier is a person who inherited the gene from one parent	214(59.4)	146(40.6)
I know about sickle cell anaemia because I have a relative/friend who has it	214(59.4)	146(40.6)
There is a cure for sickle cell anaemia	122(33.9)	238(66.1)
Drugs can cure sickle cell anaemia	64(17.8)	296(82.2)
Bone marrow transplants are the most effective cure for sickle cell anaemia	234(65.0)	126(35.0)
Sickle cell anaemia can be prevented	296(82.2)	63(17.5)

Table 1 above illustrates the knowledge of the respondents of sickle cell anaemia. The findings show that majority 261(72.5%) knew that Sickle cell anaemia is a genetic disorder that cannot be inherited from only a single parent, more so 334 (92.8%) correctly indicated that Sickle cell anaemia is a genetic disorder that can be inherited from both parents. Also, 298(82.8%) knew that in sickle cell anaemia, there is deficiency of red blood cells, 310(86.1%) indicated that the red blood cells in sickle cell anaemia are shaped like a sickle, 333(92.5%) of the respondents knew that a person who has sickle cell anaemia has the SS genotype.

Subsequently about 105(29.2%) confirmed that Sickle cell anaemia can cause partial or complete blindness, 214(59.4%) revealed that a sickle cell carrier is a person who inherited the gene from one parent, about 214(59.4%) indicated that they know about sickle cell anaemia because they have a relative/friend who has it and 238(66.1%) stated that there

is no cure for sickle cell anaemia, about 296(82.2%) indicated that drugs cannot cure sickle cell anaemia, about 234(65.0%) indicated that bone marrow transplant is the best cure for sickle cell anaemia and 296 (82.2%) indicated that sickle cell anaemia can be prevented. Aside the emphasized findings here regarding the knowledge of the respondents on sickle cell anaemia, all the findings are as depicted in table 1 above.

Figure i: Level of knowledge

Figure i shows the level of knowledge of respondents on sickle cell anaemia. Overall, it is seen that majority 290 (80.6%) had moderate knowledge of sickle cell anaemia, only 14 (3.9%) had a low level of knowledge while only 56 (15.6%) had a high level of knowledge.

Research Question 2: What are the attitudes of undergraduate students in Babcock University towards sickle cell anaemia?

Table 2: Attitude towards sickle cell anaemia

Variable	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
Sickle cell anaemia is a death sentence	42(11.7)	67(18.6)	122(33.9)	129(35.8)
Sickle cell anaemia is not the worst genetic disorder	79(21.9)	143(39.7)	59(16.4)	79(21.9)
I don't want to know my genotype status	20(5.6)	32(8.9)	85(23.6)	223(61.9)

I am aware of my genotype status	212(58.9)	90(25.0)	15(4.2)	43(11.9)
I am too young to be bothered about my genotype as I am not ready for marriage	16(4.4)	26(7.2)	92(25.6)	226(62.8)
I will carry out genotype testing before marriage	217(60.3)	92(25.6)	10(2.8)	41(11.4)
I would advise a friend to get genotype screening before marriage	237(65.8)	74(20.6)	12(3.3)	37(10.3)
All would be couples should undergo genetic screening	239(66.4)	76(21.1)	5(1.4)	40(11.1)
I will terminate my pregnancy if the pre-natal screening confirms that the baby has sickle cell anaemia	53(14.7)	49(13.6)	75(20.8)	183(50.8)
I don't believe genotype status should be hidden	206(57.2)	110(30.6)	9(2.5)	35(9.7)
Because my partner and I hardly fall sick, we are healthy and do not need to check our genotype status	25(6.9)	14(3.9)	107(29.7)	214(59.4)
Sickle cell anaemia is too costly to maintain	111(30.8)	149(41.4)	15(4.2)	85(23.6)
A person with Sickle cell anaemia is possessed and should not be near me	21(5.8)	21(5.8)	61(16.9)	257(71.4)
Sickle cell anaemia patients should be isolated from everyone else	16(4.4)	19(5.3)	61(16.9)	284(73.7)
Sickle cell anaemia patients are drug addicts and should be treated as such	19(5.3)	17(4.7)	54(15.0)	270(75.0)
I would spread rumours about my friends/relatives who has sickle cell	14(3.9)	16(4.4)	59(16.4)	271(75.3)
I can be friends with someone who has sickle cell anaemia	228(63.3)	83(23.1)	14(3.9)	35(9.7)
I can tell others that my friend has sickle cell anaemia	46(12.8)	47(13.1)	94(26.1)	173(48.1)
I will invite a sickle cell patient for lunch, to chat or for a party	193(53.6)	119(33.1)	11(3.1)	37(10.3)
I can be in a relationship with someone who has sickle cell anaemia	65(18.1)	51(14.2)	70(19.4)	174(48.3)
I will end my relationship if I find out that my partner has sickle cell anaemia	72(20.0)	64(17.8)	54(15.0)	170(47.2)
Someone who has sickle cell anaemia can live a perfect life	102(28.3)	109(30.3)	47(13.1)	102(28.3)
I would assist a sickle cell anaemia patient financially only if they ask for help	91(25.3)	139(38.6)	58(16.1)	72(20.0)
I can marry someone who has sickle cell anaemia irrespective of genotype status because all that matters is love	26(7.2)	24(6.7)	94(26.1)	216(60.0)
I cannot marry a sickle cell patient because it will cause problems in future	157(43.6)	68(18.9)	37(10.3)	98(27.2)

Findings from table 2 above showed that about (35.8%) of the respondents strongly disagree that sickle cell anaemia is a death sentence, while (39.7%) agree that sickle cell anaemia is not the worst genetic disorder with about (21.9%) strongly disagreeing. While more than half of the respondents 226(62.8%) strongly disagreed that they are too young to be bothered about their genotype as they are not ready for marriage, similarly 217(60.3%) of the respondents agreed that they will carry out genotype testing before marriage. Also, 237(65.8%) of the respondents reported that they would advise a friend to get genotype screening before marriage and majority 239(66.4%) of the respondents agreed that all couples should undergo genetic screening. More so, a minimal 53(14.7%) strongly agreed that they would terminate their pregnancy if the prenatal screening confirms that the baby has sickle cell anaemia and about 206(57.2%) of the respondents agreed that genotype status should not be hidden. Furthermore, 214(59.4%) strongly disagreed that because he or she and his or her partner hardly fall sick, that they are healthy and do not need to check their genotype status.

Majority of respondents 257(71.4%) also strongly disagreed that a person with sickle cell anaemia is possessed and should not be near them and 284(73.7%) strongly disagreed that Sickle cell anaemia patients should be isolated from everyone else. The results further revealed that 270(75.0%) strongly disagreed that sickle cell anaemia patients are drug addicts and should be treated as such, also 271(75.3%) strongly disagreed that they would spread rumors about friend/relatives who has sickle cell anaemia. It was also disclosed that 228(63.3%) strongly agreed that they will be friends with someone who has sickle cell anaemia, about 173(48.1%) strongly disagreed that they will tell others that their friend has sickle cell anaemia and 170(48.3%) strongly disagreed with ending their relationship if they find out that their partner has sickle cell anaemia.

These, amongst other things as shown in the table 2 above are the attitudes of the respondents towards sickle cell anaemia.

Figure ii: Attitudinal disposition

Figure ii shows the attitudinal disposition of respondents towards sickle cell anaemia. Overall, it is seen that majority 267 (74.2%) had a negative attitude toward sickle cell anaemia and only 93 (25.8%) had a positive attitude irrespective of the responses gotten in Table 2.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the level of knowledge of sickle cell anaemia and attitude towards sickle cell anaemia.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment correlation showing the relationship between knowledge and attitude towards sickle cell anaemia

Correlations		Knowledge	Attitude towards sickle cell anaemia	Remarks
Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	1	.113	Reject null hypothesis
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.032	
	N	360	360	
Attitude towards sickle cell anaemia	Pearson Correlation	.113*	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.032		
	N	360	360	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Results in Table 3 revealed a significant relationship between the level of knowledge of sickle cell anaemia and attitude towards sickle cell anaemia patients at ($r=0.113$, $p =0.032 <0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis (H_1) is hereby rejected which implies that there is

significant relationship between the level of knowledge of sickle cell anaemia and attitude towards sickle cell anaemia patients.

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that majority of the respondents had moderate knowledge of sickle cell anaemia, and minority of them had high knowledge of sickle cell anaemia, with fewer that had a low knowledge. However, these findings correlated with the findings of Uche, et al (2017) who assessed the knowledge, awareness and attitude of undergraduates towards sickle cell disease in Lagos, Nigeria, the study showed a fair or moderate knowledge of sickle cell anaemia. The researchers positioned that the level of knowledge was still low when compared with the percentage who had good knowledge of the condition, they ascribed the difference in the level of knowledge to indices used in knowledge assessment. Similarly, the study by Adewoyin, et al (2015) on knowledge, attitude and control practices of sickle cell disease among youth corps members in Benin city, Nigeria noted a moderate level of knowledge.

The finding also showed that most of the respondents knew about sickle cell anaemia because they had a relative or friend who has it. From the researchers' point of view, this is one of the factors promoting their knowledge of sickle cell anaemia and this view was further exposed by Boadu and Adoah (2018) who conducted a study in the university of Ghana and noted that higher levels of education and knowing a relative with sickle cell disease was significantly associated with the high knowledge of the disease among respondents Another factor could be their course of study as more than half were from the schools of science and technology, nursing and public and allied health in which a background of sciences and health is present. This view was supported in the study by Adewoyin, et al (2015) in which it was noted that those who studied courses related to medical sciences had significantly higher mean knowledge scores. The researcher is also of the opinion that at least a moderate level of knowledge was expected of respondents considering that they were university students owing to the fact that a high/moderate level of knowledge has been largely associated with tertiary institutions as exposed by Ugwu (2016) and Orish, et al (2014).

Findings from the study showed that the respondents had a negative attitude to sickle cell anaemia regardless of positive responses observed in the study. The findings are in consonance with the study of Carroll, Porter and Zhao (2015), who reported that sickle anaemia patients face stigma from different aspects or persons; peers, family, as well as health-care professionals which may come in various ways including; labelling them drug seekers, not believing that their pain experience is genuine and refusing them medication.

On the contrary, Uche, et al (2017) showed a positive attitude by respondents in spite of low knowledge as most of them (77%) agreed that haemoglobin phenotype will play a significant role in their choice of marriage partners and would consent to premarital genetic counselling. About 23% of respondents reported a fear of losing potential life partners. More so, majority of the respondents (79%) also reported an unwillingness to continue a relationship that carries the risk of having offspring with sickle cell anaemia which is also contrary to the findings from this study where majority strongly disagreed with ending their relationship if they find out that their partner has sickle cell anaemia.

Also, in the study by Anie, Egunjobi and Akinyaju (2010), a positive attitude towards respondents were noted; fair treatment by the medical staff was reported, no bullying or teasing during their education in school, college or university and no discrimination was also reported. From the researchers' point of view, this positive attitude was greatly influenced by the nature of the participants as all of them were sickle cell patients, had attained a level of

education and therefore were more informed about the disease even then, they still experienced depression imposed by their perception of the disease itself. The researchers also think that sickle cell anaemia is seen to be very costly to maintain and as a disease that affects the quality of life of the individual affected, this could promote the negative attitude and misconceptions seen amongst undergraduates and the general public towards the disease and a negative attitude towards sickle cell anaemia affects recovery and coping with the disease on the part of the individual, family and relatives affected by it.

From the results, a significant relationship existed between the level of knowledge of sickle cell anaemia and attitude towards sickle cell anaemia patients. This finding agrees with the findings of Aboagye and Aboagye (2019) on sickle cell disease: awareness, depth of knowledge and attitude towards premarital screening among students in Ghana in which an increased level of knowledge transformed into a positive attitude towards premarital counselling and also with the study of Ugwu (2016) in which majority of those who had a positive attitude towards the disease were seen to have adequate knowledge about sickle cell anaemia while the reverse was the case for those who had negative attitude.

Conclusion

In conclusion, most of the respondents had moderate knowledge of sickle cell anaemia in Babcock University. Information dissemination about the disease should be intensified both by the government and private sectors as well as religious bodies. In this way, intending couples will be encouraged to go for premarital genetic testing, newborn screenings and counselling and thus make better-informed decisions based on test results and promote the prevention of the disease.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. More awareness creation should be intensified to ensure that everyone has good knowledge of sickle cell anaemia especially by Babcock University and other educational institutions as the involvement of educational institutions in raising awareness and education on sickle cell anaemia is still low and should be strengthened
2. Couples intending to get married should endeavour to go for test to ensure that they are compatible so as to avoid producing kids with the HbSS genotype.
3. Government, schools and religious organization should discourage stigmatization being mated to sickle cell anaemia patients.
4. Government attention should be diverted to provision of comprehensive sickle cell anaemia centres with the capacity to render multi-specialist care at subsidized rates for its affected populace.

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